

Cross-linguistic competition across three languages in L3 Swedish spoken sentences

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Abstract

Efficient word recognition is crucial for speech comprehension. In multilinguals, it can be affected by parallel language activation creating cross-linguistic competition triggered by word form similarity to the input. However, findings for bilinguals' sentence processing diverge, and little is yet known about trilinguals, whose both non-target languages can compete (Bartolotti & Marian, 2018; Lijewska, 2022). This study investigated whether third language (L3) speech comprehension could be affected by lexical competition across three languages, and whether sentential context could modulate single and double cross-linguistic competition. Forty-four Russian-English late L3-Swedish learners aged 22 – 60 did a lexical selection task while listening to Swedish sentences that were low or highly constraining towards a target noun and seeing two pictures (the target and its competitor). Participants' reaction times (RTs) and accuracy were collected. The competitor's Russian phonological onset could overlap with the target's Swedish onset (e.g., /'moʎn'ijə/, 'lightning' and /mo:l/ 'goal'); the competitor could be a Swedish-English cognate (e.g., *bok* – *book*) or be a cognate and overlap (e.g., *hammare* – *hammer* – /møʎe'tok/). The results revealed shorter RTs and higher accuracy in high- than low-constraint sentences. However, phonological competition made the overall accuracy significantly lower and RTs in the high-constraint sentences longer. In contrast, single English and double Russian-English competition effects were not significant. Longer Russian-speaking country residence (or delayed L3-immersion) made the participants slower. The results suggest that top-down information from sentential context could not significantly modulate bottom-up driven first-language phonological competition. The pattern is inconsistent with the BIA+ model (Dijkstra & van Heuven, 2002) but aligns with BLINCS (Shook & Marian, 2013), which requires further investigation and suggests the need for *multilingual* mental lexicon models. The study informs on trilinguals, whose numbers are increasing but who remain unrepresented in research, and sets further questions, e.g., how language status and learning history affect cross-linguistic interactions.

References

- Bartolotti, J., & Marian, V. (2018). Learning and processing of orthography-to-phonology mappings in a third language. *International Journal of Multilingualism*, 16(4), 377–397. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14790718.2017.1423073>
- Dijkstra, T., & van Heuven, W.J.B. (2002). The architecture of the bilingual word recognition system: From identification to decision. *Bilingualism: Language and Cognition*, 5(3), 175–197. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1366728902003012>
- Lijewska, A. (2022). The influence of semantic bias on triple non-identical cognates during reading: Evidence from trilinguals' eye movements. *Second Language Research*, 39(4). <https://doi.org/10.1177/02676583221128525>

Shook, A., & Marian, V. (2013). The Bilingual Language Interaction Network for Comprehension of Speech. *Bilingualism: Language and Cognition*, 16(2), 304–324.
<https://doi.org/10.1017/S1366728912000466>